

Physical Parameter Based Compact Expression for Propagation Constant of SWCNT Interconnects

Authors : Kollarama Subramanyam, Nisha Kuruvilla, J. P. Raina

Abstract : Novel compact expressions for propagation constant (γ) of SWCNT and bundled SWCNTs interconnect, in terms of physical parameters such as length, operating frequency and diameter of CNTs is proposed in this work. These simplified expressions enable physical insight and accurate estimation of signal attenuation level and its phase change at any length for a particular frequency. The proposed expressions are validated against SPICE simulated results of lumped as well as distributed equivalent electrical RLC nets of CNT interconnect. These expressions also help us to evaluate the cut off frequencies of SWCNTs for different interconnect lengths.

Keywords : Attenuation constant, Bundled SWCNT, CNT interconnects, Propagation Constant.

Conference Title : ICEP 2014 : International Conference on Electronic Publications

Conference Location : journal city, WASET

Conference Dates : November 23-23, 2014